

ANALYSIS OF INTERFACE STRENGTH AND FAILURE MODE OF INDENTED SMA WIRE COMPOSITES

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Introduction

The interface properties of SMA wire and matrix are very important for SMA wire smart composite materials. Studies have shown that the introduction of fine indentations on the round SMA wire can significantly improve the interface performance. Through the cylindrical drawing test, based on the built-up bond-slip test system, the interface pull-slip data is collected. Combined with theoretical analysis, the bond-slip constitutive model of the interface is derived, and the critical failure stress is compared with the experimental and numerical simulation and theoretical calculation results.

Experiment

Figure (a) shows how the resin cast body sample is produced., and a pull-out test is performed on the test machine to obtain a force-time and slip-time curve to capture the initial slip point.

Figure (a) Sample preparation

Figure (b) Drawing test equipment

Figure (c) Drawing test sample force and slip diagram(The last picture is the result of the smooth SMA wire drawing test)

Bond-slip constitutive model

Obtain the τ - s curve by calculating the average shear stress. According to the bond slip τ - s curve of Figure (d), the curve can be defined in sections. It can be seen from Fig (e) that the experimental value is in good agreement with the theoretical value.

$$AB: \frac{\tau - \tau_0}{\tau_u} = C_1 \left(\frac{s}{s_u} \right)^2 + C_2 \left(\frac{s}{s_u} \right) \quad (0 < s \leq s_u)$$

$$BC: \tau - \tau_u = C_3 (s - s_u) \quad (s_u < s \leq s_r)$$

$$CD: \tau = \tau_r \quad (s > s_r)$$

Figure (d) Bond slip τ - s curve

Figure (e) Comparison of τ - s curve experiment and calculated data

Numerical simulation analysis

Based on ANSYS software, the solid element model of double cylindrical drawing structure is established in this paper.

Figure (f) Shear stress nephogram

Figure (f) 0.2mm thickness resin layer shear stress nephogram

Figure (g) Shear stress along the path

Summary

Since the experimental value uses the calculation method of the average shear stress, in the pull test, the actual shear stress has a phenomenon of end stress concentration, so the experimental value are smaller than the theoretical calculation value and the numerical simulation value. The result of finite element numerical simulation is larger than the theoretical calculation value. Therefore, the use of theoretical calculations or average stress methods in design will make the design more conservative. The relevant conclusions have a guiding role in guiding the design of SMA-based morphing composite structures.

	Experimental average shear strength value	Numerical simulation value	Theoretical calculation
Shear Stress of initial slip point(MPa)	0.7675	121.88	31.83
Shear Stress of limit force point(MPa)	2.59	413.59	110.52